

Employer Brand as a Remuneration System and Performance of County Government of Kakamega in Kenya

Esther Nafula Manyonge^{1*}, Dr. Elizabeth Nambuswa Makokha (Phd)^{1,2}

¹ College of Human Resource Development, Department of Entrepreneurship and Procurement Leadership and Management. Jomo Kenyatta University of Agriculture and Technology, P.O. Box 62000 - 00200, Nairobi Kenya

² College of Human Resource Development, Department of Entrepreneurship and Procurement Leadership and Management. Jomo Kenyatta University of Agriculture and Technology, P.O. Box 62000 - 00200, Nairobi Kenya

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Abstract: The purpose of the study was to examine the effects of employer brand on performance of County government of Kakamega. The study adopted the following theories related to the study, equity theory, Herzberg's motivator-hygiene theory, Vroom Expectancy Theory. The study applied a descriptive research design. The target population of the study was all heads of departments of Kakamega County. The study worked with entire population since the target population is small. The main data collection instrument was questionnaires. Pilot study was carried out to test the reliability and validity of the data collection instrument. Descriptive statistics data analysis method was applied to analyze data aided by Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) to compute responses frequencies, percentage mean and standard deviation results. Finally Multiple Linear Regression model was employed to establish the significance of the independent variables on the dependent variable. The findings was presented using tables. Based on the findings the study concluded the following as follows; Employee recognition ($\beta = 0.842$) was found to be positively related to performance of county government of Kakamega, Kenya. From t-test analysis, the t-value was found to be 3.756 and the p-value 0.000. Statistically, this null hypothesis was rejected because $p < 0.05$. Thus, the study accepted the alternative hypothesis and it concluded that employee recognition affects performance of county government of Kakamega, Kenya. Based on the findings, the researcher recommended the following: They should reward employees for meeting their expectations and boosts performance. They should have attractive salary increment to boost employee's morale and loyalty. Employees should be empowered through leadership opportunities and training and involvement in organizational decision making and through offering them fair gift vouchers for overall good performance to employees. Motivate employees to accomplish set targets on time, minimum supervision and provision of the conducive work environment is conducive.

Keywords: Employee Recognition; Organizational Performance.

1. INTRODUCTION

Performance is something that is often discussed to determine or provide direction for the development of the next employee. This human resource becomes a center that must be considered and addressed its performance. Human resources as employees are an important component in the delivery of services to the community. Employees will be assured of their welfare if all of the employee's needs can be fulfilled, including economic needs which in this case are realized in the system of providing performance benefits (remuneration). Therefore, the needs to be a change in the reward system that is only based on position and education, without considering the performance that has been done by employees for the organization (Siagian, 2014).

Remuneration is a part of reward received employees as a result of their task in the organization, including gifts, awards or promotions. Performance cannot be achieved optimally if remuneration is not given proportionally. Basically, the existence of these benefits has fulfilled the expectations of the staff at work. Rivai, et al (2014) explained that someone can act something (in an effort to achieve goals and fulfill responsibilities) that tends to be due to the expectation of the results to be obtained. So that when the needs and expectations of employees are fulfilled, work satisfaction can be achieved which in turn will affect work motivation. Iriani I (2020) states that Organizations in giving responsibility to employees to generate contributions in achieving goals must be balanced with reward. Providing rewards is the obligation of the organization to provide services to employees who have carried out their duties or responsibilities.

Rashmi & Ranjan (2016) affirms that “The only way employees will fulfill the employers dream is to share in their dream” Kotelnikov V, (2010). Reward system is an important mechanism that makes it happen. Employers can include recognition, bonuses, promotions, challenging assignment, or a simple thank you to motivate their employees. When employees are rewarded, they get work done and employers will get more than their expectations (Yousuf, M., & Saqib, M. (2021). Thus employees surpass their target or exceed their performance standard they should be rewarded as a way of motivating them. Motivated employees are assets for organization. A motivated person will result in a good performance as the employees know there is a reward waiting at the end of every month. Reward systems have a huge impact on organizations to retain and motivate the employees and as a result of achieving high levels of performance ((Yousuf, et al. (2021). Remuneration systems provided in an organization should aim at motivating, attracting and retaining employees in an organization to enhance better performance. However in many public organizations in Kenya, remuneration systems continues to be a major problem resulting to divined organizational performance.

Pay for performance is one of the known practices of management. All compensation designs incorporate impetus and bonus plans keeping in mind the end goal to spur workers' performance by remunerating them (Calvin, 2017). In any organization activities are performed with the assistance of assets; machine, material, cash and above all men, who make use of these assets to create value, without them different assets will be futile, torpid and won't deliver anything (Xanthopoulou et al, 2009a). Accordingly, human asset is the best resource any organization can have and ought to be given the highest priority. Human resource gives premise to an organization to attain sustainable competitive advantage (Christensen, 2011). Since organizations are working in a dynamic and aggressive business environment, they are required to develop effective strategies for acquiring and retaining competent workforce (Baker et al, 2007). In recent era, human resource is thought to be the most imperative resource of any organization and to get the productive and powerful outcome from human asset, it has become crucial to influence their attitudes and behaviours positively that leads them contributing effectively in enhancing organizational productivity by enhancing their performance (Bauer et al, 2006) Effective remuneration systems refer to the method used to reward or compensate employees for their work and services rendered to an organization. Remuneration systems should provide basic attraction to employees to perform job efficiently and effectively. Salaries affect the employees' productivity and work performance. Thus the amount and method of remuneration are very important for both management and employees (Armstrong, 2008).

Organizational performance comprises the actual output or results of an organization measured against its intended outputs (goals and objectives). Organizational performance comprises of three specific areas of organization outcomes: Financial performance i.e. profits, return on assets and return on investment, Product market performance which is sales and market share, shareholder return which is total shareholder return, economic value added. Thus, organizational performance is the most important measure to evaluate organization goals, their actions, and environments (Armstrong, 2008 & 2009).

Dong (2023) states that compensation is a crucial factor in the motivation and retention of employees in organizations. The appropriate salary compensation scheme ensures that employees feel valued and incentivizes them to contribute to the achievement of organizational objectives. Effective salary compensation is particularly important for firms operating in competitive environments where attracting and retaining skilled employees is essential for success (Loang, 2022). Despite its importance, there is a paucity of research on the impact of salary compensation on employee performance, particularly in the context of emerging economies.

Remuneration provides basic attraction for an employee to perform their job efficiently and effectively. Remuneration constitutes an important source of income for employees and determines their standard of living. It has an effect on the employee's productivity and work performance (Loang, 2022). Thus the amount and method of remuneration are very important for both management and employees. Organizational performance on the other hand may refer to whether or not

an organization is achieving its objectives. These objectives are in terms of profitability, productivity and growth amongst others. For an organization to achieve their objectives they must have in place a sufficient and efficient human resource team. This team which comprises the employees of an organization determines how well the organization performs. It is widely suggested in human resource circles that employee remuneration affects the performance of the employees and that of an organization as whole.

Organizations require exceptionally performing people, to have products and services they are specialised in, for attaining a competitive advantage, with a specific end goal to meet organizational objectives (Xanthopoulou et al, 2009b). High level performance and accomplishment of tasks can be a source of satisfaction along with sentiments of dominance and pride. Low performance and lack of accomplishment of objectives may be experienced as disappointing or even as individual failure (Coyle and Conway, 2004). Besides, performance if perceived by others inside the organization is frequently rewarded through financial and other aids. Performance is a noteworthy; although not the solitary essential requirement for future profession advancement and success in market (Masterson et al, 2000). Despite the fact of having exception, high performers are generally advanced easily within an organization and mostly have preferable profession openings comparative to low performers (Knippenberg et al, 2007).

In any organization tasks are performed with the help of resources; material, machine, money and most importantly men. All other resources except for human beings as employees are non- living. Employees make use of these resources to generate output without them other resources will be useless, dormant and will not produce anything. Therefore, human resource is the greatest asset any organization can have and should be given the highest priority. (Ojeleye & Okoro, 2016). Similar view is supported by Zaman (2011), he argued that human resource provides basis for an organization to achieve sustainable competitive advantage. Since organizations are operating in a dynamic and competitive business environment, they need to develop strategies to acquire and retain the competent workforce. He also emphasize, nowadays human asset considered to be the most important asset of any organization and in order to get the efficient and effective result from human resource motivation is necessary.

Remuneration is traditionally seen as the total income of an individual and may comprise a range of separate payments determined according to different rules. For example, the total remuneration of medical staff may comprise a capitation fee and a fee for services, or it may include a salary and shared financial risk (Buchan, Thompson & O'May, 2000). Organizations need highly performing individuals in order to meet their goals, to deliver the products and services they specialized in and finally to achieve competitive advantage. Performance is also important for the individual. Accomplishing tasks and performing at a high level can be a source of satisfaction, with feelings of mastery and pride. Low performance and not achieving the goals might be experienced as dissatisfying or even as a personal failure. The two main types of employee remuneration systems applied in the organization are time rate and piece rate systems. Under time rate system, remuneration is directly linked with the time spent or devoted by an employee on the job. The employees are paid a fixed amount hourly, daily, weekly or monthly irrespective of their output. It is a very simple method of remuneration which leads to minimum wastage of resources and minimal chances of accidents. Time Rate method leads to quality output and is very beneficial to new employees as they learn their work without any reduction in their salaries. This method encourages employees' unity as employees of a particular cadre that get equal salaries (Locke, 2008).

Piece rate method is a compensation system in which employees are paid on the basis of units or pieces produced by an employee regardless of time taken. In this system emphasis is more on quantity output rather than quality output. There is less supervision required under this method and hence per unit cost of production is low. This system improves the morale of the employees as the salaries are directly related with their work efforts (Furnham, 2009). In many organizations worldwide, remuneration package consists of a range of payment methods and accompanying benefits which can be used as motivators by modern companies and are all part of the human resource management philosophy prevalent in many organizations. In UK, employees that work for modern companies and other organizations receive a range of money based and other rewards ranging from discounts on company products, to subsidized company pension schemes (Shields, 2007). Many firms in the USA fail to measure the remuneration given to employees since compensation is a complex and often confusing topic. Although compensation costs comprise, on average, 65% to 70% of total costs in the US economy and are likewise substantial elsewhere, most managers are not sure of the likely consequences of spending either more, or less on employees or of paying employees in different ways, however, good employees remuneration systems significantly affects the performance of many organizations in USA (Armstrong, Brown and Reilly, 2009).

Loang and Ahmad, (2022) posited that in Europe, organisations remunerates employees informs of basic pay or wages, basic salary is a fixed periodical payment for non-manual employees usually expressed in annual terms, paid per month with generally no additions for productivity. Wage refers to payment to manual workers, always calculated on hourly or piece rates. Traditional pay systems were based on the three factors: the job, maintaining the level of equality in standard pay among employees in the organization, and paying competitive salaries (Braton & Gold, 2009). Armstrong, (2008), while studying the data of Employee Relations Survey conducted in England, strong evidence emerged that the use of performance related pay enhances performance outcomes, although this relationship is influenced by the structure of workplace monitoring environments. In the UK public sector, employees are paid low rate of salary compared to the private workers and this affects organisation performance (Yankee Institute for Public Policy, YIPP 2015).

In Germany, effective remuneration systems have been found to contribute towards realisation of increased organisational performance in many firms. Firms offering good basic pay and higher employees' wages higher than the market rate records increased rates of employees' job satisfaction, have lower employees' turnover rates, have most productive employees and have good employees' relations (Armsotron, 2008). In Australia, Shields (2007) study on employee's remunerations noted that basic pay is an important part of total pay that is fixed and mainly time-based, rather than performance-based. In New Zealand, basic pay is the largest fraction of the total pay for non-executive employees; it also acts as a benchmark for other cash incentives such as profit sharing, which is expressed as a percentage of basic pay. In competitive markets such in China and Japan, many organizations pay above the market rates to retain their employees. In India, most employees use basic pay to compare their job offers instead of using intrinsic rewards and other rewards not captured in the formal organizational framework.

In Africa, employees' remuneration has been ranked as major challenge affecting the performance of public sector organisations. Most public sector organisations have been found to poorly remunerate employees and this has impacted negatively on the level of employee's job satisfaction, employee's relations and productivity which contributes to declined organisations performance especially in delivery of public services (Dessler et al. (2017). Lack of effective remuneration systems leads to low basic pay and wages which leads to low employees productivity, increased staff turnover rates and declined employees morale which negatively affects the overall performance of many public sector organisations (Ologunde, Asaolu and Elumilad, 2011).

In Ghana, declined levels of employees productivity and high rate of employees turnover have been found to be influenced by employees dissatisfaction with the employed remuneration systems, increased cases of industrial strikes have been reported in public sector and this has affected delivery of public services (Hanif, 2009). In Nigeria, lack of effective employees remuneration systems have been blamed for the increased cases of industrial strikes amongst the public workers in health, education and mining sectors, these have resulted to increases rates of employees turnover due to job dissatisfaction and employees quest for better paying jobs in other countries (Oshagbemi, 2010). In Botswana, good remuneration systems in terms of better employee's salaries and wages especially in health and education sector have attracted most skilled immigrants in the country; this has also played a key role in the performance of the country's public sector organisations. In South Africa, most organizations employees' remuneration systems are either basic pay or skilled based pay. Employees use basic pay to compare their job offers instead of using intrinsic rewards and other rewards not captured in the formal organizational framework up to including job security (Livingstone, 2009). In East Africa, employee's remuneration systems have been a major challenge affecting the performance of public sector organisations. Findings from a study by Johnson (2010) revealed that majority of the employees in public sector organisations in Uganda, Kenya and Tanzania were not satisfied with their salaries and this lowered their work morale and productivity which in turn led to declined organisation performance. In Uganda and Kenya, lack of many job opportunities and increased rate of educated and qualified workers leads to increased labour supply and low labour demand which contributes to low salaries and wages.

In Kenya a significant portion of wage employment is in the public sector. One of the key issues of public debate and attention in Kenya is the public-private sector wage differentials at a time when the public sector wage bill has exceeded that of its competitors in the region. According to Kenya Institute for Public Policy Research and Analysis (KIPPRA, 2003), wage differentials have severe implication on overall productivity in the public sector and the capacity of the sector to implement policies and reforms. This has resulted in many resigning to join private sector. Those who opt to work for the government do so most probably because there is security of tenure.

Despite the fact that the Kenyan government have made efforts towards achievements of various goals, the performance of the workforce is still poor and this could be due to poor remuneration systems applied in the organizations, whereby the organizations have failed to link the remuneration systems with the skills and abilities that their employees possess and apply while carrying on their duties. This has demoralized employees leading to poor performance in many government organizations (Onyancha, 2014). For the past years, the cost of living has risen and there has been enormous pressure on employers to raise wages and salaries by the rate of inflation and change the remuneration systems in place so that they can link the systems with employee performance. It is important for the organization to consider the salary system as a mechanism by which an organization could attract, motivate and retain its employees in order to enhance its productivity through employees' performance (Onyancha, 2014). In many Kenyan government organizations, the employed remunerations systems remains a major challenge towards enhancing organizations performance. It has been observed that, remunerations systems employed leads to low level of employees' job satisfaction which demotivates most of the staff leading to poor performance, remuneration system that lead to increased staff turnover rates which affects retention of the most experienced and skilled workforce, low productivity as a result of poor performance of the employees and poor employer employee relation that result to industrial strikes (Bula, 2012).

Human capital being the most valuable asset of an organization, they are the ones that determine the success or failure of organizations' programs and activities. To maintain a hardworking, result oriented workforce, organizations should put in place remuneration systems that are meant to increase rate of employee retention in order to reduce employees turnover rates, to enhance good relations between employer and employees, increase employees productivity, employee job satisfaction to achieve organizational objectives (Livingstone, 2009). Where remuneration systems are attractive, an organization tend to save cost on recruitment since the retention rate is very high, employer employee relations is enhanced, employees are very committed with their work and their productivity is maximized which enables an organization to achieve its objectives (Stuart, 2011).

Remuneration systems refer to the compensation systems used to reward employees for their work and services in an organization. Human capital being the most valuable asset of an organization, they are the ones that determine the success or failure of organizations' programs and activities in the organization (Armstrong, 2008). Remuneration systems provided in an organization should aim at motivating, attracting and retaining employees in an organization to enhance better performance, quality work that will lead to high productivity of the organization. It is important that rewards systems should address the vision of both the company and the individual employee. Organizations have put systems in place; however, with the ever changing environment and high competition, organizations are not able to link the systems in place with employee skills and abilities they possess and apply in their performance. As a result they are not satisfied in their jobs, leading to high labor turnover, forcing organization to incur extra cost in recruitment, training and development leading to low productivity, poor employee employer relations resulting to industrial strikes and unrests thus making organizations to incur extra expenses and wasting time on court cases seeking for redress. Therefore, this study sought to examine the effects of employee recognition on performance of county government of Kakamega in Kenya.

2. EMPLOYEES RECOGNITION

In the current competitive environment, employees remain to be the overall useful resource to organizations. As a result, organizational structures are heavily dependent on employees who influence organizational mobility through their engagement, attitudes and motivation (Bruzelius & Skarvad, 2004). According to Bhattecharya and Mukherjee (2009), the future of organizations is in the hand of employees whose contributions should be optimized. Recognition has been found to be a powerful tool for motivation. Employees that are recognized are more satisfied with their jobs and are engaged in their work, which in turn makes them improve their performance as they pride themselves on more achievement for the organization they are working for. On the other hand, employees that are not properly recognized look for employment opportunities in other organizations that will appreciate their efforts (Fisher, 2016 ; Gallup, 2017). Recognition is a powerful reward that leads to improved employee performance, especially when used in an effective manner. Improved performance is positively related to organization success. Numerous studies have explored the effect or recognition on employee performance. For example, Bradler et al., (2016), performed a field investigation to evaluate the effect of unannounced, public recognition on employee performance. Workers were employed for data entry tasks and received recognition unexpectedly after two hours. Results from this study indicate that with recognition came performance increment especially when recognition is given to the best performers.

Ndungu, 2017, evaluated the effects of rewards and recognition on employee performance at Kenyatta University, Kenya. A descriptive research design was employed for this study. The sampling designed used was purposive random sampling and stratified random sampling. The study population consisted of employees of Kenyatta University main campus. Data was collected using a questionnaire that was administered to 360 employees of Kenyatta University. Inferential statistics that is regression and correlation analysis were used for data analysis. This study revealed that there exists a positive relationship between rewards and recognition systems and policies and employee performance. The study investigated an academic institution while the current study analysed the situation in a referral hospital which is characterized by a higher degree of workplace conflicts.

Muriuki, 2018, examined the relationship of recognition on employee performance at the Kenya School of Government Baringo campus. The research design used was a descriptive survey. The study population consisted of employees at different department of Kenya School of Government Baringo Campus. The sampling techniques used was Stratified sampling technique and self-administered questionnaire was used to collect the data. Analysis indicated that recognition is highly related with job performance among employees at Kenya School of Government Baringo campus. This study also presented findings in an educational institutions while the current focusses on a health institution. Whiteley (2002) hints that employees are more concerned with motivation to some extent and that one thing they have in common is that higher work motivation increase performance. To get employees to outperform during all conditions is one of the most difficult challenges managers are facing (Nohria, Groysberg & Lee, 2008).

Bruzelius and Skarvad (2004) argue that to get employees motivated to work more efficiently and to support organizational values and goals, they need a rewarding arrangement beyond salaries and wages. This arrangement should encourage skilled employees to stay within the organization as well as increase job satisfaction and commitment to the organization and thereafter increase performance (Whiteley, 2002). The environments within which organizations operate all over the world face several challenges due to the dynamic nature of the environment. The focus of every organization is growth and productivity and one of the many challenges businesses face is to satisfy the employees" in order to survive with the ever changing and evolving environment. The importance of an appropriate reward practice is seen to be the key factor in motivating employee"s performance hence organizations productivity depends on an individual or group performance. Reward practices improve performance by addressing issues such as learning and development which is basically the ability to perform a given task, reward management which is the motivation factor and Job design and employee involvement which is the opportunity given to employees to participate in decision making. Organizations adapt different ways to motivate their employees. Some use combination of intrinsic and extrinsic reward practices (Ondhowe, et al., 2021).

According to Mahaney and Lederer (2006), organizations offer intrinsic and extrinsic rewards to employees for purposes of improving human resources outcome or results. They continue to say that employees will have pride in their work when they feel motivated and believe their efforts are important to the success of the organization and their duties are challenging and rewarding. Wiscombe (2002) argued that recognition and praise are among the strong motivators. The reason for this argument is that all people like being appreciated in one way or another for their contribution at work. She further continues to say that non-cash incentives can contribute a lot to raising morale, increasing productivity, improving quality and customer service of employees and it is cost effective to the organization. Bob Nelson (2001) says that there is a strong link between non-cash incentives and improved job motivation. He thinks that non-cash incentives lower stress, absenteeism, and turnover and raise morale, productivity, competitiveness, revenue and profit.

Kaur et al., (2021) conducted a study on "Monetary Incentives Motivate Employees on Organizational Performance". This study aims to establish a connection between financial incentives and their impact on employee performance. According to the study, only financial incentives are sufficient to persuade employees across all categories to increase their work performance. Ruhnama et al. (2021) aimed at investigating the impact on relationship between financial incentives and employee's productivity. This incentive motivates employees to work in a productive way. It is the duty of personnel to transform inputs into productive outputs. Nnubia & Lovina (2020) examined the "Effect of Monetary Incentives on Employee's Performance in Manufacturing Firms in Anambra State". The study's objective was to determine the association between employee performance in manufacturing firms and bonuses, fringe perks, salaries, wages, and commissions. According to Sarah Gale (2002), non-monetary incentives are seen as more valuable incentives than monetary incentives. In her article, she emphasizes that when employees are paid for performing well in their work, then it becomes part of their salary expectations.

Yaw A. (2020) compares cash incentives with non-monetary incentives, and notes that the correlation between the monetary value of rewards and motivation is not very high and that employees who perform best in their respective jobs are not necessarily the highest-paid employees. In as much as money is a good incentive for employees, it may in the long run be disadvantageous for the organization. The reason for this argument is that employees may become accustomed to the monetary incentive or reward and start to them money as an

entitlement hence an employee may sacrifice quality to take the shortest and fastest way to maximize their monetary gain. Scott Jeffrey (2002) states tangible non-monetary incentives might be perceived as gifts that change the nature of the employment relationship. The giving of gifts or a trip to a touristic place may produce more sincere relationships that may be remembered longer and more clearly, create a positive feeling in employees than what is done with a cash bonus and this automatically increases the commitment of workers towards the organization. Wiscombe (2002) says that non-monetary incentive is the only way an organization can maintain and improve employee morale while retaining costs. Statement of the Problem Employees not only want good extrinsic compensation on the work but also want to be praised and valued for the efforts they put in on the work (Saunderson, 2004).

According to a study by Gostick and Elton (2007), organizations that have the motivational systems comprising employee recognition and appreciation are associated with higher employee morale and performance levels. According to Nyakundi, Kabare and Munene (2012), through a study at Kenyatta National Hospital, the Kenya public sector is bedeviled with poor performance due to job dissatisfaction resulting from poor intrinsic and extrinsic motivations. Another study by Muchai and Mwangi (2012) on the effect of employee rewards and recognition on job performance at Nakuru Water and Sanitation Services Company showed that recognized employees are more involved in organization's issues and perform better. However, the company had inadequate options in recognizing and rewarding their best performers. A case study by Njanja, Maina, Kibet and Njagi (2013) of Kenya Power and Lighting Company found out that when employees are recognized and rewarded, they become motivated to perform even better. They recommended that rewards have a positive effect on employee performance though no reward system is perfect because motivation is personal.

The practice of recognition has been around for a long time and yet in the modern business age, many companies do not utilize it as much and as often as they should. The impact of recognition on employee performance is quite significant. In this competitive era, where many individuals are afraid of cutbacks and pay reductions, a simple practice such as recognition of efforts can go a long way in boosting their morale and productivity (Mandra B., 2018). According to recent studies, every business that has integrated a culture of employee recognition in their workplace has seen tremendous increase in employee engagement levels. Something as simple as a „thank you“ has a profound impact on employees. It makes them feel valued and are happy that their efforts are being given due recognition. While it is a great step to initiate this practice in the workplace, there are certain ways to go about the whole process. Instead of simply asking everyone to adopt the practice of recognition in their daily routine, introduce a program which can assist employees understand the finer nuances of the process of recognition. Leverage technology to simplify the process and easier adoption (Mandra B.,2018). A well planned employee recognition program will be able to: clearly define a process on how to go about recognizing others efforts, provide the right platform where individuals can be appreciated by their peers, managers and other stakeholders and establish a clear set of guidelines about the do's and don'ts of recognition(Mandra B.,2018).

Once you have this program in place, employee recognition becomes a breeze. Here are some of the effects of a well-planned employee recognition program: Employees who are appreciated for their efforts on a consistent basis and systematically, are more engaged in their work. They understand if they are able to repeat that performance, they will again be recognized in front of their peers. Due to this, their productivity is increased to a great extent. This is in accordance with basic behavioral psychology. Like a child, we too repeat our actions to receive the same accolades. It helps the company to have employees who want to repeatedly demonstrate such behavior which makes it easy for them to link it with their KPIs in some instances (Mandra B., 2018).

Many studies have reported a significant association between remuneration systems, employees' productivity and organizational performance .Luthans (2012) study in UK showed that organizational performance was greatly determined by the level of individual employee's productivity which was determined by the organization remuneration systems. According to Luthans (2012) findings, employees who were better remunerated were more motivated and this made them to improve their level of productivity which contributed towards realization of increased organizational performance. A study by Armstrong (2008) noted that employees' remuneration system plays a major role towards determination of the

individual employees „productivity and overall organizational performance in many organizations worldwide. Lu & Barriball, (2011) showed that employees“ productivity in many organizations is determined by time taken to complete job tasks, employee productivity, and work output, level of supervision and utilization of organization resources. A study by Robbins (2011) found out that in USA, individual employees productivity was influenced by the remuneration system among other factors such as working conditions and work life balance which also affected overall organizational performance.

Luthans (2012) study detected a complex relationship between employees“ productivity and organizational performance in Australia firms. He showed that lack of better remuneration systems led to poor pay amongst many workers in public organizations and this demoralized them to improve on productivity hence leading to poor organizational performance. However, employee“s productivity was found to be higher in organizations that employed better remuneration systems and this impacted positively towards realization of increased overall organization performance.(Hong, Wei & Chen,2007) study showed that high productive employees were better remunerated in many Chinese firms and these improved overall organizational performance.

A study by Eijgendaal (2009) found out that application of poor remuneration systems in many African countries was one of the main reasons why many African organizations fail to meet their performance goals. Eijgendaal (2009) asserted that, discrimination and inequality in remuneration demoralizes many employees and this lowers their productivity and the overall organizational performance. In South Africa, Edwards (2008) revealed that there existed a strong link between remuneration systems, employees“ productivity and organizational performance. Employees who were better remunerated in many South African firms were more productive and this played a major role towards improvement of the overall organizational performance. (Edwards 2008), Kinyanjui (2012) revealed that dissatisfaction on the employed employees“ remuneration systems in state organizations led to low level of employees“ morale and job satisfaction and this lowered the level of employees productivity which impacted negatively to the overall organizational productivity. (Kariuki ,2012) study showed that lack of better remuneration systems is one of the major problems that leads to low level of employees productivity in many government corporations and this affects achievement of the their performance targets.

3. METHOD

The study adopted a descriptive research design. The target population for the study was 72, comprised of all middle level management in County Government of Kakamega, Kenya. Since the study population is small, the study will work with entire population which is census. Data collection instrument was questionnaire. Pilot test was done for testing the reliability of instruments and the validity of the study (Mugenda et.al 2009). After data is collected and all the completed questionnaires re-turned, preliminary analytical steps of editing, coding and tabulation was done. The study used both descriptive and inferential statistics to analyze the data. The coded data was entered into a computer and the SPSS computer package version 28 was used. The correlation and regression analysis was carried out in order to establish the contribution of each independent variable to the dependent variable.

4. DISCUSSION

Recognition is a powerful reward that leads to improved employee performance, especially when used in an effective manner. Improved performance is positively related to organization success. Numerous studies have explored the effect or recognition on employee performance (Bradler et al., (2016). The study sought to analyse the effects of employees“ recognition on performance of county government of Kakamega. The findings are presented in a five point Likert scale where SA=strongly agree, A=agree, N=neutral, D=disagree, SD=strongly disagree and T=total.

From table 4.1 below, the respondents were asked whether best employees are offered certificate of appreciation and featured in newsletters. The distribution of findings showed that 37.0 percent of the respondents strongly agreed, 30.0 percent of them agreed, 15.0 percent of the respondents were neutral, 13.0 percent disagreed while 5.0 percent of them strongly disagreed. These findings implied that best employees are offered certificate of appreciation and featured in newsletters.The respondents were also asked whether long service and good performance attracts salary increment.The distribution of the responses indicated that 35.0 percent of the respondents strongly agreed to the statement, 14.0 percent of them agreed, 28.0 percent of them were neutral, 16.0 percent of them disagreed while 8.0 percent of them strongly disagreed to the statement. These findings implied that Long service and good performance attracts salary increment.

The respondents were also asked whether employees are branded with attires of the organization. The distribution of the responses indicated that 27.0 percent of the respondents strongly agreed to the statement, 42.0 percent of them agreed, 27.0 percent of them were neutral, 4.0 percent of them disagreed while 0 percent of them strongly disagreed to the statement. These findings implied that employees are branded with attires of the organization.

The respondents were further asked whether performing employees committees are fully paid tickets to games. The distribution of the responses indicated that 5.0 percent of the respondents strongly agreed to the statement, 52.0 percent of them agreed, 26.0 percent of them were neutral while 9.0 percent and 8.0 percent of them disagreed strongly and disagreed to the statement respectively. These findings implied that performing employees committees are fully paid tickets to games. Also, the respondents were asked whether employees are empowered through leadership opportunities and training. The distribution of the responses indicated that 29.0 percent of the respondents strongly agreed to the statement, 51.0 percent of them agreed and 20.0 percent of them were neutral. None of the respondents disagreed or strongly disagreed to the statement respectively. These findings implied that employees are empowered through leadership opportunities and training.

Further, when respondents were asked whether employees are involved in organizational decision making and are offered fair gift vouchers for overall good performance to employees, 27.0 percent of the respondents strongly agreed, 41.0 percent of the respondents agreed on the statement, 8.0 percent of the respondents were neutral while 12.0 percent disagreed, 20.0 percent strongly disagreed. This implied that majority agreed that employees are involved in organizational decision making and are offered fair gift vouchers for overall good performance to employees.

Table 4.1: Effects of Employees' Recognition on Performance of County Government of Kakamega

Statements on employees' recognition	SA	A	N	D	SD
Best employees are offered certificate of appreciation and featured in newsletters	% 37.0	30.0	15.0	13.0	5.0
Long service and good performance attracts salary increment	% 35.0	14.0	28.0	16.0	8.0
Employees are branded with attires of the organization	% 27.0	42.0	27.0	4.0	0
Performing employees committees are fully paid tickets to games	% 5.0	52.0	26.0	9.0	8.0
Employees are empowered through leadership opportunities and training	% 29.0	51.0	20.0	0	0
Employees are involved in organizational decision making and are offered fair gift vouchers for overall good performance to employees	27	41.0	8.0	12.0	20.0

4.1 Effect of Organizational Performance in Kakamega County., Kenya

The study sought to determine effect of organizational performance in Kakamega County. The findings are presented in a five point Likert scale where SA=strongly agree, A=agree, N=neutral, D=disagree, SD=strongly disagree and T=total.

From table 4.9 below, the respondents were asked whether the provision of clear goals and objective. The distribution of findings showed that 46.0 percent of the respondents strongly agreed, 30.0 percent of them agreed, 2.0 percent of the respondents were neutral, 15.0 percent disagreed while 8.0 percent of them strongly disagreed. These findings implied that the provision of clear goals and objective.

The respondents were also asked whether customers are always served to their satisfaction. The distribution of the responses indicated that 48.0 percent strongly agreed to the statement, 35.0 percent of them agreed, and 2.0 percent of them were neutral, 9.0 percent of them disagreed while 5.0 percent of them strongly disagreed to the statement. These findings implied that customers are always served to their satisfaction.

The respondents were also asked whether there are proper placements of employees. The distribution of the responses indicated that 44.0 percent strongly agreed to the statement, 37.0 percent of them agreed, 4.0 percent of them were neutral, 7.0 percent of them disagreed while 11.0 percent of them strongly disagreed to the statement. These findings implied that there are proper placements of employees.

The respondents were further asked whether employees are focused to quality services. The distribution of the responses indicated that 37.0 percent strongly agreed to the statement, 46.0 percent of them agreed, 6.0 percent of them were neutral

while 9.0 percent and 2.0 percent of them disagreed strongly and disagreed to the statement respectively. These findings implied that employees are focused to quality services.

Finally, the respondents were also asked whether organizational performance should relate to how successfully an organized group of people with a particular purpose of commitment perform a function to achieve great results measured in terms of the value delivered to customers. The distribution of the responses indicated that 36.0 percent strongly agreed to the statement, 37.0 percent of them agreed, 4.0 percent of them were neutral, 13.0 percent of them disagreed while 10.0 percent of them strongly disagreed to the statement respectively. These findings implied that Organizational performance should relate to how successfully an organized group of people with a particular purpose of commitment perform a function to achieve great results measured in terms of the value delivered to customers.

Table 4.9: Effect of Organizational Performance in Kakamega County, Kenya

Statements on Organizational Performance	SA	A	N	D	SD
Provision of clear goals and objective	45.0	30.0	2.0	15.0	8.0
Customers are always served to their satisfaction	48.0	35.0	2.0	9.0	5.0
Employees are focused to quality services	44.0	37.0	4.0	7.0	11.0
There are proper placements of employees	37.0	46.0	6.0	9.0	2.0
Organizational performance should relate to how successfully an organized group of people with a particular purpose of commitment perform a function to achieve great results measured in terms of the value delivered to customers.	36.0	37.0	4.0	13.0	10.0

4.2 Inferential Statistics

4.2.1 Pearson Correlation

The study sought to establish the strength of the relationship between independent and dependent variables of the study. Pearson correlation coefficient was computed at 95 percent confidence interval (error margin of 0.05). Table 4.10 illustrates the findings of the study.

Table 4.10: Correlation Matrix

Performance of County Government		
Employee recognition	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000
	N	65
	Pearson Correlation	.948**

As shown on Table 4.9 above, the p-value for employee recognition was found to be 0.000 which is less than the significant level of 0.05, ($p < 0.05$). The result indicated that Pearson Correlation coefficient (r-value) of 0.805, which represented a strong, positive relationship between employees' recognition on performance of county government of Kakamega.

4.2.2 Multiple Linear Regression

Multiple linear regressions were computed at 95 percent confidence interval (0.05 margin error) to show the multiple linear relationships between the independent and dependent variables of the study.

4.2.2.1 Coefficient of Determination (R^2)

Table 4.11 shows that the coefficient of correlation (R) is positive 0.623. This means that there is a positive correlation between remuneration systems on performance of county government of Kakamega, Kenya. The coefficient of determination (R Square) indicates that 38.5% of performance of county government of Kakamega, Kenya is influenced by remuneration system. The adjusted R^2 however, indicates that 38.3% of performance of county government of Kakamega,

Kenya is influenced by remuneration system leaving 61.7% to be influenced by other factors that were not captured in this study.

Table 4.11: Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.623 ^a	.385	.383	7.3022

a. Predictors: (Constant), Employee Recognition,

4.2.2.2 Analysis of Variance

Table 4.12 shows the Analysis of Variance (ANOVA). The p-value is 0.000 which is <0.05 indicates that the model is statistically significant in predicting how remuneration system affects performance of county government of Kakamega. The results also indicate that the independent variables are predictors of the dependent variable with an F test of 74.177.

Table 4.12: ANOVA^a

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	729.845	1	111.654	74.177	.000 ^b
	Residual	1640.030	64	24.465		
	Total	2369.875	65			

4.2.2.3 Regression Coefficients

From the Coefficients table (Table 4.13) the regression model can be derived as follows:

$$Y = 52.203 + 0.842X_3$$

The results in table 4.13 indicate that all the independent variables have a significant positive effect on performance of county government of Kakamega. The influential variable is employee recognition with a coefficient of 0.842 (p-value = 0.000). According to this model when all the independent variable values are zero, performance of county government of Kakamega, Kenya will have a score of 52.203.

Table 4.13: Regression Coefficients

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
(Constant)	52.203	3.922		47.534	.000
Employee recognition	.842	.163	.336	3.756	.000

4.2.3 Hypothesis Testing

H₀₁: Employee recognition does not have a significant effect on performance of county government of Kakamega, Kenya.

From Table 4.13 above, employee recognition ($\beta = 0.842$) was found to be positively related to performance of county government of Kakamega, Kenya. From t-test analysis, the t-value was found to be 3.756 and the p-value 0.000. Statistically, this null hypothesis was rejected because $p < 0.05$. Thus, the study accepted the alternative hypothesis and it concluded that employee recognition affects performance of county government of Kakamega, Kenya.

5. CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

The study sought to analyse the effects of employees' recognition on performance of county government of Kakamega. The findings that best employees are offered certificate of appreciation and featured in newsletters and that long service and good performance attracts salary increment. The findings also indicated that employees are branded with attires of the organization and that performing employees committees are fully paid tickets to games. Further, the findings implied that Employees are empowered through leadership opportunities and training and that employees are involved in organizational decision making and are offered fair gift vouchers for overall good performance to employees.

Based on the findings the study concluded the following as follows; Employee recognition ($\beta = 0.842$) was found to be positively related to performance of county government of Kakamega, Kenya. From t-test analysis, the t-value was found to be 3.756 and the p -value 0.000. Statistically, this null hypothesis was rejected because $p < 0.05$. Thus, the study accepted the alternative hypothesis and it concluded that employee recognition affects performance of county government of Kakamega, Kenya. Based on the findings, the researcher recommended the following: They should reward employees for meeting their expectations and boosts performance. They should have attractive salary increment to boost employee's morale and loyalty. Employees should be empowered through leadership opportunities and training and involvement in organizational decision making and through offering them fair gift vouchers for overall good performance to employees. Motivate employees to accomplish set targets on time, minimum supervision and provision of the conducive work environment is conducive.

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